

A cost-benefit analysis for reconfigurable PV modules under shading

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Abstract

Non-uniform conditions within a PV module lead to significant energy losses in conventional topologies. Some of the energy lost due to partial shading can be recovered by installing reconfigurable modules. In order to explore the potential benefits of reconfigurable topologies in installations where non-uniform conditions are dominant, three shading scenarios are simulated throughout the year, both for reconfigurable and conventional modules. This allows the evaluation of the performance of each topology and estimation of the long-term gains. Using a cost function, which includes the additional investment cost, the energy gain can be translated to financial terms. Through this, locations where reconfigurable topologies can be beneficial, both in energy and financial terms, can be identified. The methodology is applied to the case of reconfigurable PV modules with a snake-like configuration. Simulation results show that these PV modules allow for higher energy production compared to conventional modules under all the simulated shading scenarios. However, they remain economically profitable over 20 years only in locations where partial shading is expected to occur daily, either throughout the full year or at least in the period of the year where energy generation is high.

Keywords: partial shading, PV module, reconfigurable topology

1. Introduction

In recent years, the Photovoltaic (PV) market has expanded and PV arrays are installed in locations which are considered far from ideal. Building-Integrated PhotoVoltaics (BIPV), Building-Applied PhotoVoltaics (BAPV) and solar vehicles are increasing, leading to a plethora of PV plants which are operating under non-uniform conditions (Kumar et al., 2018), (LIGHTYEAR, 2018), (Salfiti, 2018).

Such non-uniformity can happen at different levels and can be due to different causes. For instance, installation of PV modules on different facades of a building, as well as on different parts of a vehicle, leads to non-uniformity between the PV modules. Furthermore, objects belonging to or surrounding a given building (e.g. chimneys or trees) can cast shades onto only a part of a PV module, thus moving the non-uniformity to a sub-module level (Shukla et al., 2016), (Biyik et al., 2017). This can be even worse for solar vehicles, where the casted shade continuously changes while the vehicle is moving depending on the environment (usually urban) and the direction of the vehicle motion. Partial shading can be either dynamic or static. Dynamic shading can be caused by static objects (trees, chimneys) or by moving objects (clouds). Static shading is caused mainly due to soiling, but also bird dropping as well as localized degradation of PV modules creates static shading (Wohlgemuth et al., 2013). Operation under non-uniform conditions causes poor performance of standard series connected conventional modules (Teo et al., 2018).

A possible approach to mitigate the effects of partial shading and non-uniform conditions within the module is by allowing reconfiguration within the module and enabling control in the submodule level. The

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benefits of reconfigurable module topologies for static shading patterns have been discussed in [Baka et al. \(2014, 2016\)](#). It is shown that reconfigurable modules can recover lost power during conditions of partial shading, but produce less energy than conventional topologies under uniform operating conditions. Clearly, reconfigurable modules can be beneficial when non-uniform conditions are sufficiently present. However, this earlier work does not allow yet to quantitatively identify under what conditions gains extend beyond costs. To illustrate the potential long-term benefits of reconfigurable topologies, the performance of PV modules needs to be evaluated in realistic and dynamic shading scenarios over a longer period of time, thus a detailed simulation is required which includes time-varying effects. Ideally, one full year should be simulated, in order to account for variability of both overall irradiance and shading pattern. Results of a full year simulation can be extended to the following years by considering typical degradation rate of solar panels and power converters. Also, the cost introduced by extra components of reconfigurable modules should be taken into account.

To address this gap, in this work, an energy vs cost analysis is performed for the reconfigurable modules with a snake-like configuration previously introduced in [Baka et al. \(2014, 2016\)](#). Realistic shading scenarios are considered and the recovered energy is compared to the expected cost. It is worth to note that, although the discussion will focus on reconfigurable PV modules with a snake-like configuration, the methodology can be applied for any other module topology. This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, works which focus on the mitigation of non-uniform conditions in the PV array are presented. The cost aspects which are considered for the design of reconfigurable modules are discussed in Section 3, where both design-time and run-time instantiations of reconfigurable modules which are considered in this work are presented too. The simulation framework, the shading scenarios and the simulation results in terms of energy are shown in Sections 4 and 5. The investment cost of these topologies is discussed in Section 6, and an estimation of the financial gain is made in Section 7. Conclusion ends the paper.

2. Optimization of Performance under Partial Shading: Review of Different Approaches

Several studies focus on the optimization of the performance of PV installations under conditions of partial shading. Depending on the method applied to deal with non-uniformity, such studies can be classified in three main categories: (I) work focusing on improvement of system components, (II) work focusing on alteration of the interconnection of the PV array and (III) work focusing on introduction of extra elements in the PV array.

Improving system components, such as solar cell's efficiency and interconnections' resistance, improve the overall efficiency of the PV system under any type of operating conditions. The studies which fall into this category and target operation under non-uniform conditions are the ones which focus on the optimization and refinement of the Global Maximum Power Point Tracking (GMPPT) algorithm ([Saravanan and Babu, 2016](#)). In most PV systems, bypass diodes are present to prevent reverse-bias of PV cells and avoid the so-called hot spot ([Simon and Meyer, 2010](#)). However, bypass diodes lead to multiple peaks in the P - V (Power-Voltage) curve of the system and the PV system can either operate in suboptimal points or be stuck in local maxima. Several works focus on the improvement of Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) techniques, aiming for better speed and accuracy ([Bizon, 2016](#)), while others on the optimization of the bypass elements ([Pulvirenti et al., 2012](#)).

The second category involves studies which alter the interconnection of the PV components, without adding any new elements in the PV array. Under uniform conditions, series connections of the cells in the module and series connection of the modules themselves yield the optimal results because the systems current cannot exceed the one produced by a single cell, thus resistive losses are minimized. However, under non-uniform conditions, altering the configuration of the PV array with a combination of series and parallel connections can improve the overall performance ([Pendem and Mikkili, 2018](#)). As shown in [Braun et al. \(2016\)](#), where the standard Series-Parallel configuration of a PV array is compared to the Bridged-Link and the Total-Cross-Tied (TCT) ones under different shading scenarios, there is no absolute best configuration, since performance does depend strongly on the shading pattern. In some cases, the best configuration was based on disconnection of some PV modules from the PV array. The same approach could be applied to the modules themselves, by connecting the cells e.g. in TCT. However, scaling down to the module level comes

with two main drawbacks: such fixed configuration might be sub-optimal in many cases and the current level at the module output will be significantly big. For instance, in a standard module made of 60 cells arranged in a 10x6 matrix, TCT configuration leads to a module current equal to 6 times the current of a single cell under uniform irradiation. Since uniform conditions are likely at solar noon, extreme module current must be expected. In the modules themselves, also the configuration of diodes can be changed to minimize the power losses under partial shading (Díaz-Dorado et al., 2010).

In both categories above, the presence of bypass elements signifies that under non-uniform conditions either part of the array operates in a suboptimal point or another part is bypassed. To remedy this, in the last category, as stated, additional elements are included in the PV array. This can be further divided in static configurations and dynamic configurations of the PV system. Addition of elements in static configurations of the PV system include distribution of the MPP tracking, such as Power Optimizers (Olalla et al., 2014) and Micro-Inverters in different levels of the PV array (Pragallapati and Agarwal, 2013), and the increase of the number of bypass diodes applied to allow a finer granularity level of non-uniformity mitigation (Wardle et al., 2011). The presence of bypass elements implies that instantaneous power can be potentially bypassed or reduced. On the other hand, static distribution of the MPP tracking leads to unnecessary active elements under uniform conditions which increase the power and resistive losses. For instance, any power optimizer must continuously process the whole power produced by a PV module, independently of the presence of non-uniformity within the module itself (Spagnuolo et al., 2015). This leads to additional losses even when the power optimizer is not needed at all. PV modules equipped with power optimizers and microinverters can be already found on the market nowadays (solaredge, 2018), (Enphase, 2018). Such "smart" PV modules still have a conventional configuration, with three substrings protected by one bypass diode each. Although proper GMPPT algorithms can improve the performance of such PV modules under shading (Vinnikov et al., 2017), they are still coarse-grained, so that up to 1/3 of the module can be bypassed even if only one cell is significantly shaded. A different approach has been proposed by Maxim Integrated (2018), where bypass diodes are replaced by substring-level power optimizers (JinkoSolar, 2018). Again, granularity is still too high and inter-module non-uniformities are not properly addressed. To improve granularity, a bigger number of smaller substrings must be created within a module. If the approach proposed by Maxim Integrated (2018) is used, the cost of the module will significantly increase, since one power optimizer is needed per substring.

Dynamic configurations of the PV array involve the addition of dynamic elements which allow reconfiguration of the array at run-time. Together with a matrix of switches allowing for real-time implementation of different interconnection schemes, this type of approach requires also a control mechanism to determine the optimal configuration according to the operating conditions. For a detailed description and comparison of reconfiguration strategies for PV systems, the interested reader is referred to La Manna et al. (2014) and Spagnuolo et al. (2015). The selection of the reconfiguration algorithm impacts the cost in two different ways. On the one hand, highly complex algorithms, as in Fathy (2018) and Rajan et al. (2017), require expensive devices to be executed. On the other hand, every algorithm requires a specific set of measured variables to be executed properly. In some cases, only electrical measurements are needed in different points of the PV system, as for the technique proposed by Cipriani et al. (2014). In other cases, also non-electrical variables such as irradiance and ambient/module temperature (Vigni et al., 2015) must be measured. Depending on the number and type of variables to measure, the additional cost and complexity related to the reconfiguration algorithm varies from negligible to significant (Spagnuolo et al., 2015). A detailed analysis of how the choice of the reconfiguration algorithm affects the investment cost is done in Section 6. The work discussed in this paper falls into the third category and specifically it involves a dynamic internal reconfiguration of the PV module. The goal of this reconfigurable topology is to increase the energy produced under non-uniform conditions while maintaining a high performance under uniform operating conditions with reasonable additional cost. The PV modules considered here show significant gains in installations where non-uniform operating conditions are frequent. This work focuses on the development of a methodology for assessing the economical benefit of these reconfigurable modules.

3. Design criteria for reconfigurable modules

The goal of our approach is to increase the overall energy yield of a PV module by enabling control in the submodule level. It is evident that additional elements required for the fabrication of reconfigurable modules increase the manufacturing cost. Furthermore, the added elements in the active current path induce power losses which must be taken into account. The way cost and gain relate each other is fundamental for designing reconfigurable modules. Such relationship between cost and gain is discussed now in more detail.

The gain of reconfigurable modules stems from energy recovered during non uniform operating conditions. When cells of the module have different $I-V$ (Current vs. Voltage) characteristics, altering their interconnection can increase the overall module performance: whenever non-uniform conditions are present, a reconfigurable module can recover energy which otherwise would be lost (Baka et al., 2016). Degradation of cells through time can also lead to non-uniformity. Under such degradation conditions, the use of reconfigurable topologies can be very beneficial. Moreover, the expected level of non-uniformity within the module plays an important role to the overall gain which can be obtained by applying reconfiguration. This recovered energy accumulates throughout the lifetime of the module.

Reconfigurable modules require inclusion of additional elements in the module. These elements introduce resistive losses when they are active. The goal of reconfiguration is to come as close to a custom designed topology for the specific operating conditions by utilizing dynamic and knob-controlled elements (Baka et al., 2014). Given that extra devices are present, the active current path deviates from the minimal required, and part of the energy is consumed in additional resistive losses. Also, degradation of extra components through time leads to additional inefficiencies. Furthermore, these elements occupy area which is excluded from producing any energy. All these energy losses are again accumulated throughout the lifetime of the module. Finally, the investment cost has to be taken into account. This mainly involves the initial cost of the module; cost of additional elements, manufacturing, fabrication cost and maintenance cost.

The recovered energy and the energy losses can be expressed in financial terms by considering both Feed-in tariffs and savings due to self-consumption. This allows the formulation of (1), where $G(t)$ and $C(t)$ are the gain and cost which accumulate over time respectively, T is operation time and IC is the investment cost.

$$T \cdot [G(t) - C(t)] - IC > 0 \quad (1)$$

A positive value of the left part of Eq. (1) translates to a gain which compensates for all the cost. The dominant cost aspect is the time dependent cost which is present whenever the module is in operation. Thus, the electrical losses are the most significant cost factor over a long-term usage in an environment where non-uniform conditions are reasonably common but where uniform conditions still occur for the majority of the time. The goal is to maximize the time-dependent term by improving the time-dependent gain, while simultaneously reducing the time-dependent cost. And as an overall design constraint, a reasonable investment cost should be maintained as manufacturers do not want their sales prices to be much above the one of standard modules. These cost aspects are partly dependent on one another. To increase the power harvested under partial shading conditions requires flexibility and a finer granularity level which in consequence increases the time-dependent cost as more resistive elements are present and the investment cost as the module becomes more complex. This is not straightforward and a simulation process is needed to find the best trade-off.

3.1. Snake topologies

The methodology proposed here can be applied for any module topology. In this work it will be demonstrated for snake topologies which have been shown to be promising. In Baka et al. (2016) the general template of snake topologies is discussed. Snake topologies, are a subcategory of reconfigurable PV module topologies. The basic concept of reconfigurable topologies is to minimize mismatch losses by reducing the granularity level of the PV module and enabling reconfiguration depending on the operating conditions of the module itself. The minimum element is called a cell-string which comprises of permanently series connected cells. The size and geometry of the cell-string is decided at design time and determines the flexibility

Figure 1: Design-time instantiation of (a) I-type and (b) U-type module with four local converters (boxes with red borders) and one module converter (box with green borders)

of the PV module. The cell-strings in snake topologies are basically U-shaped and the name derives from the shape of the connected cells in series. Two templates of reconfigurable modules are proposed. They are called I-type and U-type and are illustrated in Figure 1(a) and Figure 1(b), respectively. The cell-layout of these two topologies differ in the cell-strings located at the edges of the module. Cell-strings are represented by blocks with orange borders in Figure 1. Such proposed reconfigurable topologies have two main classes of run-time instantiations (Baka et al., 2016):

- 1) "All cell-strings connected in series (AiS)", which is optimal when the module operates under uniform conditions. Under uniform/near-uniform conditions, there is no real issue for mismatch occurrences between the cell-strings and a single configuration is available. To have all cells connected in series is optimal as the current level is equal to the current produced by a single cell and the resistive losses are kept minimal. To realize this instantiation, shown in Figure 2(a), the reconfiguration switches depicted by small blue and white boxes in Figure 1 are open, whereas the ones depicted with small black boxes are closed. One converter (module converter), depicted by a block with green borders in Figure 1 and Figure 2, is active under such instantiation. It allows module-level MPPT, in order to cope with intra-module mismatch. The cell-layout of the I-type is better than in the U-type as shorter wires are active when all cell-strings are connected in series.
- 2) "Groups of cell-strings connected in parallel to local converters (GoP)", which is optimal for operation under partial shading conditions. Under non-uniform conditions, the cell-strings are connected in parallel to avoid large mismatch losses; voltage is not so sensitive to partial shading (Piegarì et al., 2015). However, the parallel connection of cell-strings increases the current level and thus the resistive losses. The number of parallel-connected cell-strings in a group should not exceed a certain value (depending on the electrical characteristics of the cells), as the gain from avoiding mismatch losses would not compensate for the increased resistive losses. Currents of parallel-connected cell-strings sum up and must flow to the module converter. Local converters are placed to reduce the current on BUS and Ground line, which are the thick continuous black line and the thick dashed black line in Figure 1 respectively, and to keep their resistive losses low. The module converter is connected to the outputs of the local converters to further boost the module voltage for connection with the rest of the PV array. To realize this instantiation, shown in Figure 2, the reconfiguration switches depicted by small blue and white boxes in Figure 1 are closed, whereas the ones depicted with small black boxes are open. In this configuration, the U-type module has a better division of the cells than the I-type in the vertical direction for the entire length of the module.

Figure 2: Two run-time instantiations of I-type module. (a) AiS and (b) GoP

Hybrid types of run-time instantiations are also possible and can lead to increased energy efficiency. Depending on the operating conditions, the cell-strings within a group can be connected in series, cell-strings can be isolated or local converters can be bypassed. Thus, several configurations are available, but their similarity allows to treat them as one configuration.

4. Simulation Framework

In order to estimate the accumulated gain and losses which are mentioned in Section 3, the overall energy of the module needs to be computed. The evaluation of the performance of the module topologies is done through simulation. This allows the comparison of different configurations of the module under the exact same external conditions. In [Manganiello et al. \(2017\)](#) a simulation setup is developed which allows an accurate comparison of energy generation of different PV module topologies under non-uniform and dynamic operating conditions. In this work, the simulation of reconfigurable topologies is analyzed.

The wires and switches are implemented in the simulation environment as electrical resistances. The resistances of wires are computed based on their dimensions (Table 6). Switches' ON resistance is taken as $3.6\text{m}\Omega$ ([Bauwens and Doutreloigne, 2015](#)). Simulation does not include an analytical model for converters. Instead the converters are modeled in a behavioral way. The local converters are considered to have a constant 95% efficiency, while the module converter is assumed to have an efficiency of 98%. The conventional module in this work is equipped with a power optimizer which has a constant efficiency of 98%.

Simulation of AiS run-time instantiation and conventional modules. In conventional modules and in the AiS run-time instantiation of reconfigurable topologies, only one converter is active, the module converter, performing a module-level MPPT. A transient analysis with a MPPT algorithm at the module converter is performed in these cases. A perturbation period of 50ms has been considered, so that a timestep of 50ms is set for the solver.

Simulation of GoP run-time instantiation. In the group configuration of parallel cell-strings, four local converters and the module converter are active. The model includes all elements up to the input ports of the local converters. Ideally, having all potential operating points for each converter ($I-V$ curves) would allow a better exploration of the combination of operating points which maximize the module's instantaneous power. However, the increased simulation time required and the lack of an analytical model of a converter make this type of analysis unrealistic. A transient analysis is performed and the voltage of each converter is determined by a distributed MPPT algorithm: each local converter performs the MPPT of the group

Figure 3: Generation of Shading Scenarios. The module at the right of the chimney is used to generate SS1, whereas the module at the left of the chimney is used to generate SS2. Four screenshots are shown in the figure, referring to four different times on September 17th, 2014: (a) 8:20, (b) 9:20, (c) 13:20 and (d) 14:20

of parallel-connected cell-strings connected at its input. Again, a perturbation period of 50 ms has been considered. During this instantiation, the module converter is not performing any MPPT. It is instead fixing its input to a given voltage level, that is it is applying a given fixed voltage to the local converters' output. Given this value, the conversion ratio of every local converter can be evaluated, thus the current on the BUS and the Ground lines is known. Such simulation procedure allows an estimation of the gain of reconfigurable modules under realistic dynamic operating conditions, which is the goal of this work. However, a more accurate converter behavior, e.g. where efficiency is not fixed but it changes according to the operating conditions and the efficiency diagrams of the converter itself, and a faster simulation environment are needed and constitute future work.

As the reconfiguration algorithm has not been implemented, each run-time instantiation is simulated independently. The power of the AiS and GoP configurations are compared and the configuration with the highest power is selected. This also provides information about the operating conditions which should trigger a reconfiguration and can be used as input to develop a run-time control mechanism. Transitions are not frequent and simulation results are accurate assuming a reasonable run-time reconfiguration scheme. Proper selection of the reconfiguration algorithm is necessary also to keep additional cost low. A detailed analysis of how the choice of the reconfiguration algorithm affects the investment cost is done in Section 6, where also guidelines for selection/design of such algorithm are provided.

4.1. Shading Scenarios

In order to estimate the potential energy gain of reconfigurable topologies, three different Shading Scenarios with different characteristics have been considered. Modules were placed virtually on a south-oriented house's rooftop in Oldenburg, Germany. This location has been selected since data from a monitoring station located there are available. The monitoring station includes a measurement setup which stores the required meteorological data (Direct and Diffuse Irradiation, Wind Velocity, Ambient Temperature) with a 1 second time resolution ([University of Oldenburg, 2014](#)). The shading scenarios are generated by using the SketchUp

software (Trimble, 2018) which enables creation of oriented 3D geometries, and allows geo-location and date and time specification. Thus, the real sun path and the orientation of the module as well as the surrounding objects are taken into account in the casted shades.

The two first shading scenarios are considered to be more likely. The objects casting the shades are located near the module and cast shades throughout the year, causing significant non-uniformity within the module. In the first shading scenario (SS1), the module is partially shaded by a chimney in the afternoon. In the second shading scenario (SS2), the module is shaded by a chimney in the morning and by part of the roof in the evening. The generation of SS1 and SS2 is shown in Figure 3. The module at the right of the chimney is used to generate SS1, whereas the module at the left of the chimney is used to generate SS2. Given the simulated location of installation (Oldenburg, Germany), the orientation of the roof (the part of the roof where the modules under analysis are installed is facing South), and the fact that the two modules considered for SS1 and SS2 are positioned in portrait and landscape orientation, respectively, they will be subject to two shade patterns that move mainly along the short and the long edge, respectively. The shades of SS1 and SS2 are perpendicular to one another. This renders these two scenarios complementary and it is possible to extrapolate from them the behavior of shading scenarios with different orientations of shade.

In the third scenario (SS3), that is more of an outlier, the module is shaded by a tree for part of the afternoon. The casted shade is highly irregular and because of the size of the tree at some moment covers the entire module, leading to more frequent uniform conditions of the module. Moreover the tree does not cast shade on the module throughout the whole year. No wind is considered in SS3, since the object causing the shade is a tree, which is an obstacle affected by wind.

For each shading scenario, shading tables were created. Combining these shading tables with given Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) and Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI), the global in-plane irradiance of each cell N can be computed.

The objects which cast the shade are opaque and near the module, thus direct irradiation is considered to be completely blocked by shade. However, how the objects affect diffuse irradiation has some uncertainty (Perez et al., 1987). In order to cover the entire range, three possible options were taken into consideration.

- 1) DHI is completely blocked by objects ($x = 1$), i.e. the shaded part of cells does not receive any diffuse irradiation.
- 2) Half of DHI is affected by objects ($x = 0.5$).
- 3) DHI is not affected at all by objects ($x = 0$).

It is worth to note that, as long as there are sunlight shading effects, they will not completely cancel the irradiation. However, given the complexity of the simulated cases, setting a maximum value for x is not straightforward. Thus, for practical purposes, the entire range of possibilities has been explored, meaning from $x_{min} = 0$ to $x_{max} = 1$. The irradiation of the illuminated part of the N -th cell, $G_{N,ill}(t)$, is calculated based on Eq. (2), where SP_N indicates how much of the cell N is shaded, in percentage. The incident irradiation of the shaded part, $G_{N,sh}(t)$, depends on the value of x as shown in Eq. (3). The total irradiation of each cell N , $G_N(t)$, is the sum of Eq. (2) and Eq. (3), as shown in Eq. (4).

$$G_{N,ill}(t) = (1 - SP_N(t)) \cdot (DNI(t) + DHI(t)) \quad (2)$$

$$G_{N,sh}(t) = SP_N(t) \cdot (1 - x) \cdot DHI(t) \quad (3)$$

$$G_N(t) = G_{N,ill}(t) + G_{N,sh}(t) \quad (4)$$

5. Simulation Results

5.1. Effect of diffuse irradiation

When DHI is completely blocked by objects ($x = 1$), the irradiation differences within the module are larger and the degree of non-uniformity within the module is highest, out of all the three cases. As fully

shaded cells do not receive any irradiation, they do not contribute to power generation. In conventional modules this means that when not all bypass sections are affected, the bypass diodes of the shaded sections are active as to not compromise the operation of the rest of the module. Recovered energy in reconfigurable modules is attributed to illuminated cells which do not compromise their operation due to series connection with shaded cells.

In the second case, where only part of DHI is affected by objects ($x = 0.5$), shaded cells receive some irradiation, thus can partly contribute to power generation. Similarly, in the third case ($x = 0$), shaded cells have a higher irradiation level as DHI is not affected at all and their contribution to power generation is higher. The Maximum Power Point of conventional modules can either lie in the region where shaded sections are bypassed or in the region where the overall current of the module is reduced, depending on the level of irradiation differences. Recovered energy in reconfigurable modules is both due to independent operation of fully illuminated cells, that is more likely given their finer granularity, and extraction of power from shaded cells.

5.2. Performance for the selected Shading Scenarios

First simulations have been performed for the three shading scenarios by considering a single day (17/09/14). The daily energy produced by the different modules (conventional, I-type and U-type) for the three values of parameter x are listed in Table 1. Also, the gains of reconfigurable modules with respect to the conventional one are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1: Energy Production: 17/09/2014 - Oldenburg

Shading Scenario	Topology	Energy (kWh)		
		$x = 1$	$x = 0.5$	$x = 0$
SS1	Conventional	0.6431	0.6630	0.6804
	I-type	0.7293	0.7414	0.7558
	U-type	0.7323	0.7438	0.7574
SS2	Conventional	0.5810	0.5891	0.6374
	I-type	0.6773	0.6979	0.7232
	U-type	0.6812	0.7007	0.7248
SS3	Conventional	0.5777	0.6033	0.6436
	I-type	0.6413	0.6651	0.6929
	U-type	0.6466	0.6695	0.6962

Table 2: Gains w.r.t. Conventional module: 17/09/2014 - Oldenburg

Shading Scenario	Topology	Gain (%)		
		$x = 1$	$x = 0.5$	$x = 0$
SS1	I-type	13.40	11.83	11.08
	U-type	13.87	12.18	11.33
SS2	I-type	16.57	18.48	13.46
	U-type	17.23	18.95	13.73
SS3	I-type	11.01	10.24	7.66
	U-type	11.92	10.98	8.17

SS1. As expected the overall energy increases in all configurations as irradiation which reaches the shaded cells increases. This extra energy (in the case where $x = 0.5$ and $x = 0$) is attributed to the increase of power contribution of the shaded cells when the module is partially shaded. The gains of the reconfigurable modules are higher when all of the diffuse irradiation is blocked, as the presence of high degree of non-uniformity compromises severely the performance of the conventional module.

SS2. Again it can be observed from Table 1 that the overall energy increases as the incident irradiation on shaded cells increases. What should be noted from Table 2 in this shading scenario is that the highest gains in percentage are when part of the diffuse irradiation is affected by the shading objects ($x = 0.5$). It can be seen that the increase of daily energy of the conventional module between the cases where all diffuse ($x = 1$) and part of the diffuse is affected ($x = 0.5$) is really small. This is due to the shape of the casted shade for this scenario on this specific day (the sun path varies throughout the year) and the creation of local maxima in the instantaneous $P-V$ curve of the conventional module. Two out of three bypass sections are partially shaded almost all morning, whereas the third one is partially shaded only at early morning (see Figure 3(a) and Figure 3(b)). When the incident irradiation of the shaded cells increases, as part of the diffuse irradiation reaches the shaded cells, some of the local maxima change, namely the one(s) which lie in regions where the shaded cells are not bypassed. As the change of these is not as significant as in the case where all diffuse irradiation reaches the cells ($x = 0$), the overall energy of the module does not improve so much. In other words, in the cases ($x = 1$) and ($x = 0.5$), two subsections of the conventional module are often bypassed, whereas in the case ($x = 0$) the power produced by the shaded subsection(s) is enough to allow it(them) to conduct and the relative bypass diode(s) to be deactivated. Reconfigurable modules however can extract some extra power from the shaded cells and thus the gain is increased. When all DHI reaches the shaded cells ($x = 0$) and the degree of non-uniformity within the module drops, the energy of all configuration increases and the respective gains of reconfigurable modules are lower than in the other two cases.

SS3. The results between the different values of x , both in energy and in gains, are similar to the ones of SS1, which is expected, as the shade often affects all bypass sections of the conventional module simultaneously.

5.3. Uniform conditions

Finally, the performance of these three module topologies (conventional, I-type and U-type) have been compared for a location where no shade is cast. The results of this simulation are listed in Table 3. Under constant uniform conditions, both reconfigurable topologies have losses compared to a conventional module, 0.60% and 0.77% for the I-type and the U-type respectively. Based on the energy produced in a uniform day by a conventional module, the losses due to shading can be calculated for each shading scenario.

Table 3: Energy under uniform conditions: 17/09/14 - Oldenburg

Topology	Energy (kWh)
Conventional	0.8208
I-type	0.8159
U-type	0.8145

5.4. Long term energy gain

In order to estimate the annual gain of reconfigurable modules, one day has been simulated for each month (March-November). The selected days are representative of each month's average irradiation profiles. For every month, first, the average monthly profiles of DNI and DHI , represented as $\overline{DNI}_{month}(t)$ and $\overline{DHI}_{month}(t)$ respectively, are calculated. This calculation is shown in Eq. (5) for $\overline{DNI}_{month}(t)$. Then, the monthly representative day is selected as the one that is the closest to the average profiles in a weighted root-mean-square (RMS) sense. Weights are calculated as from Eq. (6) and Eq. (7), where DNI_{month} and

Figure 4: Irradiance profiles of selected days, one per month from March to November: (top) DNI and (bottom) DHI.

DHI_{month} represent the monthly cumulated DNI and DHI , respectively. The selection of the day is finally done according to Eq. (8).

$$\overline{DNI}_{month}(t) = \sum_{day} DNI_{day}(t) \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, 86400 \text{ s} \quad (5)$$

$$W_{DNI} = \frac{DNI_{month}}{DNI_{month} + DHI_{month}} \quad (6)$$

$$W_{DHI} = \frac{DHI_{month}}{DNI_{month} + DHI_{month}} \quad (7)$$

$$\arg \min_{day} [W_{DNI} \cdot \text{RMS}(DNI_{day}(t) - \overline{DNI}_{month}(t)) + W_{DHI} \cdot \text{RMS}(DHI_{day}(t) - \overline{DHI}_{month}(t))] \quad (8)$$

DNI and DHI for the selected days are shown in Figure 4. The winter months have been excluded due to low irradiation levels. During these months, the diffuse irradiation is dominant and, the level of non-uniformity within the module is extremely low. These days can be simulated as uniform days. Moreover, the daily produced energy during winter in the selected location (Oldenburg) is extremely low.

Shading tables have been created for the selected days, as the sun path changes throughout the year. During June and July, the tree casts no shade on the module (SS3) and the module operates under uniform conditions for the entire day.

Table 4: Average Gains throughout the year

Shading Scenario	Topology	Gain (%)		
		$x = 1$	$x = 0.5$	$x = 0$
SS1	I-type	9.67	8.26	4.68
	U-type	10.29	8.61	4.81
SS2	I-type	18.32	15.17	8.31
	U-type	18.76	15.36	8.32
SS3	I-type	2.04	1.84	1.03
	U-type	2.27	1.91	1.02

The average annual gains for all values of x are shown in Table 4. The gains are significantly higher for SS1 and SS2 where the casted shade is caused by objects with clear cut edges and partial shading occurs throughout the year. It should be noted, that for SS3 there is still some gain, although there is no shade during June and July which are months with high irradiation levels, thus high energy production. It can be seen that the U-type module outperforms the I-type for all shading scenarios. This means that the complete split achieved by the U-type is significant for the given simulated scenarios, as the U-type suffers more losses during uniform operating conditions. The only case where the I-type module outperforms the U-type is in the SS3 when $x = 0$ (diffuse irradiation is not affected by the shading objects). As the degree of non-uniformity is smaller and in this shading scenario uniform conditions are more frequent, the losses in uniform conditions become more significant.

6. Investment Cost

In an instantiation of a snake topology with X cell-strings, the numbers of added discrete elements are shown in the Table 5. One column shows the added elements for a generic template with X cell-strings, while the other shows the discrete elements which have been added for the configurations examined in detail in this work. Three different types of switches are present in the table. The distinction is made based on their use and the conditions that they should withstand when they are active or inactive.

Table 5: Number of components in reconfigurable modules

Component	X cell-strings	10 cell-strings
Switches between cell-strings	X-1	9
Switches between cell-strings and ground line	X-1	9
Switches between cell-strings and converters	X+1	11
Local converters	n	4
Module converter	1	1

Switches between cell-strings are used to connect the cell-strings in series. The number of switches required for this is equal to $X - 1$. In this case, the module is divided in 10 cell-strings, thus 9 switches between cell-strings are needed. When these switches are active they carry at most the current of a single cell. When they are inactive, the voltage across them is the operating voltage of a cell-string, given that only the two main classes of run-time instantiations are enabled.

Table 6: Wire Dimensions in reconfigurable modules

Type	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)
Accumulative Bus	5	0.5
Ground Line	10	0.5
Between Cell-strings	4	0.3
Cell-strings to Converters	4	0.3
Cell-strings to Ground Line	4	0.3
Converters to Ground Line	10	0.5
Converters to Accumulative Bus	4	0.3
Perpendicular connection within a U-shaped cell-string	4	0.3
Long wire in U-type module	5	0.5

Switches between cell-strings and the ground line connect the negative terminal of a cell-string to the ground line. As one cell-string is connected to the ground line in both main classes of run-time instantiations, such cell-string is permanently connected to the ground. Thus, $X - 1$ switches are needed. When active, these switches carry the current of a single cell. However, when they are inactive, the voltage across them is higher and depends on their position in the module, reaching at most the operating voltage of the entire module.

The other type of switches is the one connecting the cell-strings to the converters. In the series connection, one cell-string is connected to the module converter. In the parallel case, all cell-strings are connected to local converters. This leads to $X+1$ potential connections of cell-strings to converters. This illustrates that the number of switches is not related to the number of local converters, but solely to the number of cell-strings in the module (granularity level). Once again, the current flowing through these switches never exceeds the current of a single cell. As the converters are also inactive when the switches are inactive, the voltage across them when they are inactive is not solely determined by the module layout, as it also depends on the actual design of the converters.

The additional wires needed for the interconnections of the elements of the reconfigurable module cannot be addressed with number of connections, as the extra metal required depends on the design of the module. As mentioned above, in this work, the module template is optimized to reduce the additional power losses, while maintaining reasonable investment cost. The dominant added wires in reconfigurable modules are the accumulative bus and the ground line which surround the module as seen in Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 1(b). Shorter wires are needed to connect cell-strings to cell-strings, cell-strings to converters, cell-strings to the ground line, converters to ground line and converters to the accumulative bus. Additional metal is also used for connecting cells perpendicularly within a U-shaped cell-string and for the long wire required to connect "neighboring" cell-strings in the U-type module. For each category of connections, different dimensions of wires are used. The thickest and widest (thus less resistive) wires are used for the accumulative bus and the ground line, since these wires surround the entire module, i.e. they are the longest, and carry the highest current.

To estimate the total amount of metal needed for a specific design instantiation of a PV module, some other dimensions are needed as well. The cell size, that is $12.5 \times 12.5 \text{ cm}^2$ for the selected cells and the cell spacing, that is kept to 2 mm, as in current standard modules. Two-busbars cells are considered, where the distance between the busbars is 6.2 cm and the distance between a busbar and the edge of the cell is 3.15 cm (BP Solar, 2005). The exact location and placement of the local converters and the module converter are needed to calculate the length of all wires. Once the length of the wires is calculated, based on the dimension of the cells and the spacing, and by taking into account the dimensions of the cross section of wires depending on the type (see Table 6), the total volume of required metal can be computed. By converting the volume to mass, and by using the price of metal per kilogram the cost of the extra wires can

be calculated. Cost of metal is dominant to evaluate the cost of the extra wires. Indeed, in reconfigurable Snake PV modules, additional wires are laminated within the module itself, meaning that they are not external cables. Thus, no other material than the bare metal is needed. Also, stringing is done as in conventional PV modules, although small changes in the production line are needed to add switches and to allow stringing along both sides of the module. Depreciation of these production line adaption are not included in our cost analysis at this stage, since they would become less significant compared to the cost of extra material for mass production of reconfigurable Snake PV modules. Last but not least, as any other PV modules, Snake modules have only two output nodes, namely the output of the module converter. Thus, their connection to the rest of the string is done as usual. It means that no any additional installation cost are expected when using reconfigurable Snake PV modules.

As an illustration, for a placement of the 4 local converters in the middle of their corresponding groups of cell-strings and by using a price of 4.25 € per kilogram of copper, the extra cost for wires for the I-type and U-type is 1.62 € and 1.65 € respectively. By assuming the cost of each switch equal to 0.10 euros (Bauwens and Doutreloigne, 2015), the additional initial manufacturing cost is 4.52 € for the I-type and 4.55 € for the U-type plus the cost of the four local converters and the module converter, which has not been computed still. So far, the cost of the module converter can be reasonably assumed equal to the one of power optimizers. Thus, it can be taken out of the equation, since we are considering conventional modules equipped with power optimizers. The cost of the local converters depends on their design and their characteristics and the goal is to have a set of local converters which in total do not exceed 12-15 €.

Furthermore, the reconfiguration algorithm itself affects the total cost of the module. Reconfiguration algorithms are presented in literature that do make use of external sensors, e.g. temperature sensors as in Tria et al. (2009) and Vigni et al. (2015). If one of these algorithm is used, the cost of the additional sensors must be included in the cost analysis. To eliminate this additional cost, reconfiguration algorithms that rely only on module-level electrical measurements, e.g. voltage or current within the module itself, must be selected. Ideally, voltage sensors should be favoured to current sensors, given their lower cost. Last but not least, computational burden of the reconfiguration algorithm must be kept low, to be able to use low-cost microcontrollers. As a consequence, despite their good performance, Artificial Intelligence-based reconfiguration algorithms, as the ones presented in Fathy (2018) and Rajan et al. (2017), should be avoided since they usually require expensive embedded devices to run properly. Algorithm as Cipriani et al. (2014) should be preferred, since they only require voltage sensing per cell-string and the reconfiguration algorithm simply rely on comparison between the measured voltages and a threshold. Such simple reconfiguration algorithms can be likely executed by the same microcontroller that run the MPPT algorithm embedded in the module-level converter. If a solution like this is implemented, the only additional cost is the one of the voltage sensors and the related wirings: the former must be included, whereas the latter are signal wires, with a very small cross-section, so that their cost is negligible compared to the additional cost of the power wires, as described previously in this Section. It is worth to note that, compared to conventional modules, some additional sensing is done by design in reconfigurable Snake PV modules. Indeed, in order to perform distributed MPPT, voltage and current are measured at the input of local converters. This information, together with the voltage and current measurements performed at module-level by the module converter, can be used to develop an ad-hoc reconfiguration algorithm, to be implemented on the module-converter microcontroller. There is no additional cost related to the reconfiguration algorithm itself in this case, since the cost of sensors and microcontroller is already included in the converters cost. Development of such control algorithm represents future work.

7. Energy vs cost

In order to estimate the energy recovered throughout the year, the energy produced by a conventional module working for a full year under uniform conditions has been evaluated by simulation. For the conventional module used in this work, this value is equal to 162.70 kWh. Based on both this value and the average losses due to partial shading in each shading scenario, the annual energy produced by the conventional module for each shading scenario has been evaluated. Finally, by applying the average gains of Table 4, the

annual energy production of reconfigurable modules in each shading scenario has been estimated. Only the case $x = 0.5$ has been considered since it is the most realistic value of the parameter x .

By using these results, a prediction of the financial gain allowed by the proposed reconfigurable modules in 20 years has been performed. In order to be more realistic, degradation effects and changes in the electricity price have been taken into account. Degradation is separated into two categories, degradation of the cells and degradation of the additional electronics. From the warranty of modules, a uniform degradation of the cells is considered which is a 1% yearly linear degradation (Jinko Solar, 2014), (SolarWorld, 2016). This affects both conventional and reconfigurable topologies. Degradation of additional electronics concerns only the reconfigurable modules. A model of the performance degradation of additional electronics is not available, but based on the warranty of electronics (solaredge, 2016), an additional linear degradation of 0.5% per year is considered for the recovered energy of reconfigurable topologies. The current average price of electricity in Germany is equal to 0.29 €/kWh (Eurostat, 2017). Starting from this value, an increase of this price with a rate of 2% per year (Eurostat, 2017) is assumed. A 20-year prediction of the net additional financial gains allowed by reconfigurable modules replacing conventional ones in each shading scenario is shown in Table 7. The values shown in Table 7 represent the left part of Eq. (1). They are positive for SS1 and SS2, meaning that under such shading scenarios the overall gain compensates for the cost. Thus, for the given environmental input and electricity price, SS1 and SS2 represent cases in which it is financially worth to install reconfigurable Snake modules instead of conventional ones, whereas reconfigurable Snake modules are not well suited from a financial point of view for shading scenarios as SS3. The net financial gain shown in Table 7 refers to one single I-type/U-type Snake module replacing a conventional one under the simulated scenarios and for the given cost of electricity. Thus, if e.g. 10 modules in a PV system are working under a shading scenario as SS2, replacing conventional modules with U-type Snake modules will lead to 10 times 88.74 € net financial gain over 20 years in a climate like the one of Oldenburg (Germany), considering the German price of electricity for household consumers. Note that a lower net financial gain (per module) is expected in the case of non-residential applications, since non-household consumers usually get a lower electricity price.

Table 7: Net financial gain due to self-consumption, in 20 years

Module type	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
I-type	46.99 €	87.44 €	-4.18 €
U-type	49.77 €	88.74 €	-3.64 €

8. Conclusion

The potential benefit of reconfigurable PV modules in installations where non-uniform conditions are prevalent has been explored. Operation under three different shading scenarios has been considered and the performance of reconfigurable topology has been benchmarked to the one of conventional modules. A cost function has been defined and used for estimation of financial gain, so that it has been possible to analyse the potential benefit of reconfigurable solution in both energy and financial terms.

It has been observed that reconfigurable topologies outperform conventional modules when partial shading occurs. When partial shading conditions are present throughout the year, the gains are significant (5-15%) as shown for shading scenarios 1 and 2. In the third shading scenario, non-uniform conditions are not present during June and July, where energy production is very high, and thus the gain drops to 1-2%. Financial gain depends on the amount of recovered energy and on the location of the installation (price of electricity, Feed-In Tariffs). The energy gains of scenarios 1 and 2 are sufficient to ensure long-term financial gain, while the amount of energy recovered in scenario 3 is not enough to compensate for the initial cost. This signifies that reconfigurable topologies should be installed in locations where non-uniform conditions are expected to be present throughout the year or in the period of the year where energy generation is high. The fact that the U-type outperforms the I-type module for all shading scenarios illustrates that the

complete split of the cells in both directions can be beneficial even if it implies bigger losses in uniform conditions.

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